

GST in Informal Sector: Some Insights from the Guwahati City of Assam

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Abstract

GST in India was aimed at creating a common, unified and integrated domestic market, allowing the free flow of goods and services across different Indian states making conducive platform for economies of scale of big businesses. But it nullifies regional tariffs creating detrimental position for informal sector and small businesses. The informal sector in India is mostly unregulated and untaxed. Despite being unregulated, informal sector has been reported as one of the most important sectors for economic growth of the Indian economy. But haphazard implementation of GST has reduced the competitiveness of the informal sector creating problems of viability of the sector which in turn limits the potential entrepreneuriality of the region. Subsequently, general people dependent on the unregulated informal sector especially the non-salaried people of the country expressed their widespread dissatisfaction over GST. Based on the statement, the study endeavours to investigate to assess the different economic impacts of GST especially on non-salaried individuals of informal sector particularly in the Guwahati city in Assam. Using descriptive statistics and graphical tools, the study revealed that GST in India has negatively impacted the consumption pattern resulting from higher prices of goods and services which in turn, adversely affected the informal sector. The study also showed that most of the respondents viewed GST as an unfair tax and badly affected people's lifestyle and income in the post-GST period.

Keywords: Descriptive statistics, Entrepreneuriality, Informal sector, Non-salaried persons, Taxation.

JEL Classification: E26; H21; H26

Introduction

Tax is a compulsory monetary payment to state, levied by the government on its worker's overall income. Taxes are levied primarily to raise revenue for government expenditures providing welfare services to its citizens in returns. Direct taxes are

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imposed mainly on the income of the individual, whereas indirect taxes are imposed on goods and services. Unlike direct tax, indirect tax is usually borne by the end consumers including rich and poor people. Some of these indirect taxes are levied by state government whereas some are levied by central government in most countries including India. All types of indirect taxes in India, however, are unified into one tax formally known as Goods and Services Tax (GST) implemented on July 1, 2017 in the country.

Thus, GST has replaced all the existing indirect taxes as well as the multiple cascading taxes levied by the government including taxes at every step in the production process. The GST is divided into five tax slabs for collection of tax, i.e. 0%, 5%, 12%, 18% and 28% slabs. However, only some products namely petroleum products, alcoholic drinks, and electricity are not covered under GST. But these products are taxed separately by the state governments. Moreover, precious and semi-precious stones are taxed at a special rate of 0.25% and gold at 3% slab. However, all the tax slabs and other special tax rates of GST are subject to change time to time.

The main aim of the GST was to create a common, unified and well-connected domestic market which, in turn, will help the free flow of commodities across different states of the country realizing the economies of scale of all kinds of businesses especially for manufacturing sectors of the Indian economy. But the GST nullifies regional tariffs, hence, creating detrimental position for informal sector and small businesses. Several studies argued that because of the GST implementation the Indian economy is expected to unify regional markets and overall tax burden of goods and services, with reduced tax evasion and distortion, will reduce which covers almost 25% to 30% of the tax (Vasanthagopal, 2011; Sarma & Baskar, 2012; Mussaiyib, 2016; Devi, 2016). Additionally, the impact of the GST on agricultural sector has been expected to be positive because one of the major issues faced by the agricultural sector is the transportation of agriculture produces across state all over India. It is highly probable that the GST shall resolve the issue of transportation across the states in the country.

One of the main characteristics of Indian informal sector is that this sector is mostly untaxed and unregulated. However, the informal sector of India reported as being one of the valued sectors of Indian economy for rapid economic growth. This sector contributes about 31% of the country's gross domestic product (GDP) and nearly half of India's total exports employing about 30% of the labour force of the country according to the Govt. of India (Annual Reports of 2007-18 to 2015-16, Ministry of MSME, New Delhi). However, large part (almost 24 percent) of this share comes from MSME service

sector in comparison to the MSME manufacturing sector which contributes about 6 percent of the total MSME's contribution. However, more than 90% of these enterprises are unregulated and unregistered in India. Thus, the above mentioned figures can even be greater if the informal sector is included in the economy.

According to the International Labour Organization (ILO), informal employment consists of about 62% of all workers in the world and constitutes almost 90% of workers in low-income countries, 67% in middle-income and 18% in high-income countries (ILO, 2020). But growth of these sectors in India has gone through many ups and downs especially constrained in the last decades especially the sudden instigation of demonetization of Indian currency in 2016 and haphazard execution of GST (Goods and Services Tax) in July, 2017. One recent study by Ghosh (2020) stated that implementation of GST reduced the competitiveness and the problem of viability of the informal sector will emerge. That is why; this type of reform must be implemented systematically and judiciously (Purohit, 2020). Hence, GST became onerous for the informal sector and its growth has been thwarted by the implementation of GST (Banerjee & Prasad, 2017; Bhattacharjee & Bhattacharya, 2018; Srinivasan & Shankar, 2018). Furthermore, unprecedented and unexpected outbreak of COVID-19 has worsened the situation leading to massive employment loss and output fall.

As informal sector units will be unregistered, their inability to raise a GST compliant invoice will hamper the input tax credit transfer to formal units lower down in the supply chain. This will force to formal players to either shift to other formal sources leading to a marginalization of informal services and manufactures. To avoid losing market shares, informal businesses will have to formalize. Admittedly, formalization is not necessarily something to forebode. The informal sector by operating outside the ambit of legislation is the breeding ground for a host of labour violations including minimum wages, discrimination, working environment, and other exploitative practices, etc. This results in substantial exploitation of labour in the informal sector, both in terms of precariousness of employment and paucity of wages. But with formalization of these units into mainstream economy, their labour too will obtain access to legal rights and redressal mechanisms and possibly better wages and working and employment conditions.

Besides, formalization will also allow informal units to access credit from financial institutions. Moreover, GST is not entirely free from criticism and contradiction as triggered by academicians and media persons. The opposition parties reported that there is no difference between the GST and the existing taxation system in the country

and claimed that it is merely a rebranding of the current taxation system. Besides, they argued that the GST would increase existing rates on necessary goods while reducing rates on luxury goods hence it adversely affects many common Indians especially the middle and lower income groups of the population. In addition, electronic bill payments of some specific value fall under GST.

However, after the implementation of the GST general people especially non-salaried people of the country expressed their mass disapproval and dissatisfaction over GST because it levies and collects tax at each stage of sale or purchase of every goods and services. So, we have to pay this tax in every step or moment of time which affect us positively as well as negatively. Thus, based on the above background, we want to explore the different economic impacts of GST through qualitative perception.

Objectives of the study

The present study endeavours to investigate the different economic impacts of GST on non-salaried individuals from the informal sector measuring through qualitative perceptions particularly in the city of Guwahati in Assam.

Method

Sampling and Data Collection

This study is based mainly on primary data which has been collected through direct personal interview with the help of a structural schedule employing the simple random sampling of data collection, we have collected a sample of the study is 100 respondents subject to time constraint and other limitations from the occupational segment of non-salaried individuals in the informal sector. The data collection has been done in the months of October and November, 2020. The study has been carried out in the Guwahati city of Assam.

Statistical Tools and Methods

The study employed different statistical tools and methods based on the collected data. The socio economic characteristics of the respondents as mentioned in the first objective was investigated with the help of statistical tools like descriptive statistics, frequency distribution, percentage tabulation, bar and pie diagrams.

Results and Discussion

Socio-economic Status of the Respondents

It is important to know their socio-economic conditions can be explained with the help of different social parameters like occupation, education, and other various demographic features. Table-1 displays that the major occupations in sample are wage earners, street vendors, and self-employed persons sharing 24%, 26% and 28% of the sector respectively. However, the share of drivers stands at 14%. The table indicates that most of the non-salaried persons in the informal sector in Guwahati city are wage earners, street vendors, and self-employed. Figure-1 shows that 30% of the respondents have at least primary and 44% of them are secondary level education. But only 4% and 2% of them are graduates and post graduates respectively.

Table-1: Occupational Structure of the Respondents

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Wage Earners	24	24%
Street Vendors	26	26%
Self Employed	28	28%
Drivers	14	14%
Others	8	8%

Source: Field Survey

Figure-1: Educational Level of the Respondents

People’s Perceptions about GST

Figure-2 displays that only 78% of the respondents are aware of GST as reported by the field survey and the rest of them are not aware of GST at all which may be due to their lack of higher education among the non-salaried persons.

Figure-2: Awareness of GST among the Respondents

It is found that most of the respondent did not accept that GST is a fair tax but if we observe the following table (Table-2) regarding age-wise distribution, it reveals that GST is completely not fair for the respondents with age 30 years or less but other age groups accepted it positively and Table-3 shows all the wage earners viewed that GST is not fair. In addition, most of all other age groups also stated GST as being not fair.

Table-2: Fairness of GST according to Various Age Group

Age Group	GST is Fair	GST is not Fair
Below 30	0%	100%
30-40	23%	77%
40-50	17%	83%
50-60	33%	67%
Above 60	50%	50%

Source: Field Survey

Table-3: Fairness of GST according to different Occupation

Occupation	GST is Fair	GST is not Fair
Wage Earners	0%	100%
Street Vendors	60%	40%
Self Employed	36%	64%
Drivers	29%	71%
Others	25%	75%

Source: Field Survey

Impact on Prices

From the qualitative analysis of the opinion about GST, it is found that most of the respondents (about 70%) voted that their life after implementation of GST has been badly affected (Figure-3). The prime reason of the badly affected lifestyle could be inflated prices of goods and services after GST implementation. Table-4 displays that 82% of the respondents reported that the prices of food items has increased after the introduction of GST in Guwahati city whereas only 14% of them reported the opposite. Similarly, it also displays that most of the respondents (94%) reported that the price of non food items also increased after GST whereas only 4% of them said that it has decreased.

Figure-3: Impact of GST on Lifestyle

Table-4: Impact of GST on Price of Food and Non Food Items

Impact on Price	Food Items		Non Food Items	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Increased	82	82.0	94	94.0
Decreased	14	14.0	4	4.0
Can't Say	4	4.0	2	2.0

Source: Field Survey

However, Figure-4 exhibits the seriousness or severity of this impact of GST on overall price including food and non-food items. It shows that 54% of the respondents agreed that GST has affected the price very much and 26% said it has slightly affected whereas 20% of them don't know about the impact.

Figure-4: Severity of GST on Price

Impact on Income

When asked about possible income variation, it is found that 48% of the respondents reported their income being badly affected and 16% of them have voted the impact of GST on income was very bad and even worst in post-GST era.

Figure-5: Impact of GST on Income

Conclusion

The study has exhibited that how the potential entrepreneuriality of the informal sectors has been affected due to the unexpected implementation of GST in India. We have seen that GST in India has negatively impacted on the consumption pattern in India resulting from higher prices of goods and services affecting the informal sector the most especially wage earners, street vendors, self-employed, drivers, and many more. The study shows that most of the respondents accepted that GST is not a fair tax and lifestyle in the post-GST period has been badly affected. The percentage of respondents who reported GST is bad is very high amongst all other opinions. Such effect has been seen as higher prices of both food and non food items. The findings show that 82% of the respondents reported that the prices of food items and non-food item has increased in the post-GST period in the Guwahati city whereas only small proportion of the respondents stated price decline.

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